

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH ON THE PREVALENCE OF
WORM INCURSION AND INTESTINAL PROTOZOA AMONG
CHILDREN WHO MIGRATED FROM NORTH WAZIRISTAN
IN THE SKIRMISHING STATE****¹Dr. Adil Khan, ¹Dr. Kanwal Shamraz, ²Dr. Ramisha Ali**
¹DHQ Teaching Hospital Sahiwal, ²Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Abstract**

Objective: The objective of this research study was to check the widespread intestinal protozoan and worm infection in young ones. These young ones were from those families who due to operation resettled to another area.

Methods: The time period for this illustrative and cross-sectional study was from August to October 2017. The study was organized in Jinnah Hospital, Lahore. The age limit of children included in this study was from 6 – 16 years. There was no specification of gender. To check the presence of intestinal protozoan and worm infection in children, stool specimen was assembled. This specimen was tested by direct light microscope.

Results: In this study, total of 150 children were assessed for the presence of worm infection and intestinal protozoa. The children who were 52 (34.66%). Presence of any oystlova was not observed in these children. The children positive for this assessment were 98 (65.33%). Presence of many intestinal parasites was observed in these children. The different parasites were Ancylostoma duodenal, Giardia Lamblia, Entamoeba histolytica, Taenia saginata, Pinworm, Hymenolepis nana, Ascaris lumbricoides, Present in the ratio of 5 (2%), 5 (3%), 9 (16%) 18 (12%), 22 (15%) and 27 (18%) respectively.

Conclusion: The factors that contribute to the widespread intestinal worm infection were dirty standing water, excretion in the open area and cleanliness.

Keywords: Intestinal Worms, INCURSION, IDPs.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Adil Khan,
DHQ Teaching Hospital, Sahiwal.

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Please cite this article in press Adil Khan et al., A Cross-Sectional Research On The Prevalence Of Worm Incursion And Intestinal Protozoa Among Children Who Migrated From North Waziristan In The Skirmishing State., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(01).

INTRODUCTION:

The prevalence of intestinal worm infection in children is high in countries which are on the way of development. To control this serious issue, there is a need for a suitable step [1]. Only 3.76% of budget was allocated for health in 2010 [2]. According to recent researches, the incidence of health infection among people is increasing around the globe, in the developing countries, the presence of intestinal worm infection is reported in approximately two billion people [3]. The incidence of intestinal worm infection is high in 5 to 15 years. During this duration, the rate of intestinal helminthic infection is high [4]. Different factors contribute to widespread of intestinal worm infection like uncleanliness, low standard of living and inadequate clean linen of surroundings [5]. In underdeveloped countries, parasitic infections are managed through targeting on regular anthelmintic treatments. Parasitic infection is still common in endemic localities [6]. Low living standard, uncleanliness and personal hygiene contribute to prevalence of parasitic infection. Worms like *Hymenolepis nana*, Threadworm (*Strongyloides stercoralis*), Tapeworm (*Taeniasaginata*, *Taeniasolium*), Pinworm (*Enterobius vermicularis*), Whipworm (*Trichuris trichuria*) and Roundworm (*Ascaris lumbricoides*) are observed these areas. These worms are probably dangerous for health [7 – 9]. The children of 5 to 10 years, 12% of all diseases is the load of worm and protozoan infections. These parasitic infections cause various health deficiencies like protein-energy malnutrition is caused by whipworm, growth is stunted and anemia is caused by whipworm influx whereas, deficiency of iron is caused by worm and intellectual growth is altered due to infection of worms. The incidence of worm infection is high in people whose standard of living is low. The incidence is also high in those people who are working outside with contaminated soil [10]. In

hookworm and *Strongyloides stercoralis*, infection is caused by infective larva entering the skin. Whereas, in a, *Lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichuria*, infective eggs cause the infection [11]. The aim of present study was to check the incidence of intestinal worm infection in children. These children belong to those families who shifted to another area (IDB).

SUBJECTS & METHODS:

The time period for this illustrative and cross-sectional study was from August to October 2017. The study was organized in Jinnah Hospital, Lahore. The age limit of children included in this study was from 6 – 16 years. There were no specification offender. To check the presence of intestinal protozoan and worm infection in children, stool specimen was assembled. The guidance was provided regarding the assemblage of enough stool (about 8 – 12 gms) by the collection team. The samples were sent to the lab and tested by light microscope, Before the confirmation of these samples by a pathologist, they were first assessed by an expert technician. Normal Salina and Lugol's iodine was used for examination.

RESULTS:

Total children in this study were 150. The number of children registered in schools in their home areas was 90 (60%). The children who were negative in their stool assessment were 52 (34.66%). Presence of many intestinal parasites was observed in these children. The children positive for this assessment were 98 (65.33%). Presence of many intestinal parasites was observed in these children. The different parasites were *G. Lamblia*, *A. Duodenal*, *E. histolytica*, *T. saginata*, Pinworm, *H. Nana* and *A. lumbricoides* in the ratio of 5 (3%), 3 (2%), 9 (6%), 14 (9%), 18 (12%), 22 (15%) and 27 (18%) respectively.

Table – I: Number and Percentage Worm Cases (Positive and Negative) (150)

Infestation Cases	Number	Percentage
Positive Children	98	65.33
Negative Children	52	34.67

Table – II: Number and Percentage Age Incidence of Various Worms

Worm	Number	Percentage
G. Lamblia	5	3
A. Duodenal	3	2
E. Histolytica	9	6
T. saginata	14	9
Pinworm	18	12
H. Nana	22	15
A. Lumbricoides	27	18

DISCUSSION:

The objective of this research study was to check the widespread intestinal protozoan and worm infection in young ones. These young ones were from those families who due to operation resettled to another area. The age limit for these children was between 6 and 16 years of age. Some similar research studies were conducted in some other parts of the country. These studies illustrated that the incidence of intestinal that incidence of intestinal worm infection is high mostly in children. This result is comparable to our study. The ratio of infection in our study. The ratio of infection in our current is 65.3% while that of conducted in another district is 54%. It showed that our ratio is greater. Different worms were present in different percentages. The most commonly noticed was Roundworm i-e A. Lambercoides.

The incidence of presence was 18%, 12% and 15% for A. Lumbercoides, Pinworm and H. Nana respectively. Comparative to various research studies organized in different areas of the world as well as in different areas of Pakistan the results of the current study are similar. 21% to 91% was the extent of worm infection reported by these research studies [12]. A prediction was made by World Health Organization (WHO) regarding the effectivity of Necator Americanus, Ancylostoma, Duodenal, A. lumbricoides and Trichuris trichiura. Similarly, 250 million and 151 million people were affected by A. lumbricoides and Ancylostoma, Duodenale respectively [13]. A. lumbricoides, Ancylostoma and for Trichuris trichuria affected approximately half the population of South India [14] and 50% of school children of tribal areas of Central India [15]. The

ratio of 64.4%, 10.9% and 1.1% was observed by Nigerian study for A. lumbricoides, Hookworms and Hookworm and A. lumbricoides was observed in 33 children while poly-parasitism in none [16]. Similar research studies were organized in different regions of India. The incidence of intestinal worms was checked through these studies. The prevalence was 30-50% as noticed through these studies [17]. The attack of intestinal parasites observed for different countries as 44%, 19.3%, 47.2% and 31.8% in Sudan, Iran, Afghanistan and Turkey respectively [18, 19].

Among teenagers [20]. Widespread intestinal infection was observed as 77% as indicated by some studies conducted in Pakistan. Comparatively, the incidence is lower as shown by Ethiopian research studies [21]. Uncleanliness, dirty water for drinking purpose, Insufficient Health Facilities, Insufficient Education, and low socio-economic status are some factors responsible for widespread of worm infections [22]. 52.8% was the percentage of presence of intestinal infections in the town area of Karachi [23,24]. Most of the people who belong to outer part of Abbottabad were a victim of A. lumbricoides (48% of positive cases) and 81% of children were a victim of intestinal worm infection [25]. The ratio of worm infection illustrated by our study was 65.33%. this percentage is greater than all the studies conducted previously [26]. The most common infection reported in the affected areas is A. Lumbricoides. For the management of this infection, there is a requirement for awareness and proper treatment. The endorsement of the World Health Organization is inscribed by us. According to (WHO), awareness should create regarding widespread worms and the deworming program should be advanced in areas where there is a high

incidence of worm infection [27].

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that the incidence of worm infection is greater in children of IDPs. Awareness should be provided to such parents regarding proper medication for the treatment of infection. They should be motivated to visit a physician for a proper dose of medicine. Furthermore, to prevent this infection, there is a requirement of proper cleanliness of drinking purpose and personal hygiene like and personal hygiene like the washing of hands after excretion.

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